

The values of A and B constants for a given polymer-solvent system at a given temperature (recorded in Table 2) have been obtained by using the

TABLE 2			
<i>Polymer-Benzene Systems</i>			
A	0.890	1.14	0.78
B × 10 ³	3.63	3.13	3.22
<i>Polymer-Water Systems</i>			
A	2.06	-0.40	-0.05
B × 10 ³	3.06	5.00	2.98

method of least squares, from the intercept and slope of the plots of $[\eta]$ vs M in the modified Staudinger equation⁴:

$$[\eta] = A + BM \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The results indicate that equation (1) holds good to a fairly good extent in the case of low molecular weight polyoxyethyleneglycol fractions as has been found by Moacanin⁵ during his study of polypropylene oxides (ranging in molecular weights from 120 to 2000).

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Flow Behaviour of Bentonite Suspensions in Presence of Electrolytes

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THE modification of flow behaviour and flocculation of clay suspensions upon electrolyte addition has many important technological applications.

The viscosity of a suspension is always higher than that of the pure medium and can more or less quantitatively expressed through a modification of the theoretically deduced Einstein formula

$$2.5\phi = \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

whereas ϕ is the total volume of the dispersed particles divided by the volume of the sol, and η and η_0 are the coefficients of Newtonian Viscosity for the suspension and pure medium respectively.

Real systems, however, show considerable deviation from equation (1) due to the non-ideal conditions, e.g., non-spherical shape of suspended particles, particle-particle and particle-medium interactions. The particle-particle and particle-medium interactions are highly sensitive to electrolyte addition in clay suspensions, which is reflected in their flow behaviour.

Experimental

"Ecogel" bentonite suspensions were prepared and characterised following the procedures reported in our earlier works.^{1,2,3} 100 ml. portions of the suspension of desired clay content were thoroughly mixed with different quantities of N NaCl solution and left overnight. The necessary volume correction was made in computing the electrolyte content and clay content of the suspensions. The viscosity measurements were made using a thermostated Ostwald viscometer and the density measurements at the corresponding temperatures were made using a thermostated pycnometer. About 1 hour time was allowed for temperature equilibration. The viscosity of water and density at the required temperatures were obtained from standard tables. To safeguard against water evaporation and consequent concentration change of the suspensions, the suspension containers were kept in a water filled desiccator.

Results

The viscosity data for clay suspensions of different clay contents in the presence of varying amounts of sodium chloride at 35°, correct to second place of decimals is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VISCOSITIES OF CLAY SUSPENSIONS (CENTIPOISES) AT 35°C IN PRESENCE OF VARYING AMOUNTS OF ELECTROLYTE (SODIUM CHLORIDE)

Sl. No.	Electrolyte Concentration (N)	Percentage of Clay				
		0.1%	0.2%	0.3%	0.4%	0.5%
1	0.0	0.74	0.77	0.81	0.84	0.85
2	0.002	0.73	0.76	0.78	0.82	0.91
3	0.004	0.74	0.76	0.80	0.84	0.97
4	0.006	0.73	0.77	0.79	0.85	1.02
5	0.008	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.89	1.05
6	0.010	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.91	1.09